

FABRICATION, STRUCTURE, AND MAGNETIC PROPERTIES OF CARBON/NICKEL FERRITE (NiFe₂O₄) COMPOSITE NANOFIBERS

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Carbon/NiFe₂O₄ composite nanofibers have been successfully fabricated by electrospinning method using a solution that contained polyacrylonitrile (PAN) in *N,N'* dimethylformamide (DMF) solvent as polymer sources and 10 wt.% of Ni and Fe nitrates solution as alternative metal sources. The as-spun and carbonized PAN/NiFe₂O₄ composite samples were characterized by TG-DTA, XRD, SEM, TEM, Raman spectroscopy and SAXS, respectively. It has been found that, the morphologies and the crystal size were influenced by the stabilization time and the carbonization temperature. A full phase of NiFe₂O₄ embedded carbon fibers was formed after carbonization in argon atmosphere at 1000 °C. The shrinkage diameter and porous surface were present after carbonization. The average crystallite sized (D) were found to be 30.9 and 30.1 nm for the samples stabilized at 280 °C for 0.5 h and 2 h, respectively. The magnetic properties of the prepared samples were measured at room temperature by a vibrating sample magnetometer. Both samples stabilized for 0.5 and 2 h exhibit ferromagnetism having saturation magnetizations of 0.36 and 3.40 emu/g, respectively.

Keywords: NiFe₂O₄, Carbon nanofibers, Magnetic/carbon composite, Magnetic properties.

1 Introduction

Carbon nanofibers (CNFs) composited with soft magnetic elements have received much attention due to their unusual properties, including large surface to volume ratio, chemical and thermal stability, high thermal and electrical conductivity and high mechanical strengths. Especially, nanocrystalline ferrites with the general formula of MFe₂O₄ (M = Co, Cu, Mn, Ni, or Zn) are very important magnetic materials because of their high saturation magnetization and high permeability. Therefore, the carbon/magnetic composite nanofibers have been received much attention for numerous applications, such as in electromagnetic shielding coating [1], catalyst [2], super-capacitor [3], and rechargeable batteries [4, 5].

In the present work, we report the fabrication of carbon/nickel ferrite (NiFe₂O₄) composite nanofibers using electrospinning technique followed by stabilization and carbonization process, respectively. Electrospinning is a simple and efficient method for preparing polymer fibers and ceramic fibers with both solid and hollow interiors that are exceptionally long in length, uniform in diameter ranging from tens of nanometers to several micrometers.

The structure and morphologies of the composite samples were characterized by thermogravimetric-differential thermal analysis (TG-DTA), X-ray diffractometer (XRD), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), transmission electron microscopy (TEM), Raman spectroscopy and small angle X-ray scattering (SAXS). Magnetic properties of the samples were also measured at room temperature by vibrating sample magnetometer (VSM).

2 Experimental

PAN/NiFe₂O₄ composite nanofibers were prepared by electrospinning using a 10 wt.% PAN solution in DMF. Nickel ferrite embedded PAN fibers were obtained by using a composite solution of 10 wt.% of Ni(NO₃)₂·6H₂O and Fe(NO₃)₃·9H₂O dispersed into PAN solution in DMF. The solution was electrospun at room temperature in an ambient air atmosphere using our home-made electrospinning system, under the following conditions: applied voltage of 17 kV, flow rate of solution at 0.5 ml/h, distance from syringe nozzle to collector of 15 cm. After the PAN/NiFe₂O₄ composite is formed into fibers, it must then be stabilized to prevent the fibers from

melting or fusing together during the high temperature heat treatment required to form carbon fibers of high strength and modulus. This step was carried out via heating rate of 5° C/min in air atmosphere at 280 °C for 0.5 and 2 h, respectively. If not assisted by chemical means, such as air or other oxidizing agents, stabilization can require many hours. On the other hand, if an acrylic polymer is heated rapidly, a violent exotherm occurs, producing fragmentation of the chain into an assortment of oligomers, as well as copious quantities of hydrogen cyanide and ammonia [6]. The carbon/NiFe₂O₄ composite nanofibers were obtained by carbonized NiFe₂O₄/PAN nanofibers under an argon atmosphere via a heating rate of 10 °C/min for 2 h at 800, 900, 1000 °C, respectively. The as-spun PAN/NiFe₂O₄ composite nanofibers were subjected to thermogravimetric-differential thermal analysis (TG-DTA, PerkinElmer Instrument, USA) for determining the temperatures of possible decomposition and crystallization of the as-spun nanofibers. The morphology and the structure of as-spun PAN/NiFe₂O₄ and carbon/NiFe₂O₄ composite nanofibers were investigated using a scanning electron microscopy (SEM, LEO 1450VP, UK), a transmission electron microscopy (TEM, TECNAI G²20 S-TWIN at 200 kV, Philips, Eindhoven, The Netherlands) and a small angle X-ray scattering (SLRI, BL 2.2). The phase of the carbonized samples were identified using a Philips X-ray diffractometer (XRD, PW3040, The Netherlands) with Cu K α radiation ($\lambda=0.15406$ nm). The structures of the CNFs and carbon/NiFe₂O₄ composite nanofibers were investigated by Raman spectroscopy (JOBIN-YVON T64000 Micro-PL/Raman spectroscopy, $\lambda=514.5$ nm). The magnetic properties such as saturation magnetization and coercivity of the carbonized samples were examined at room temperature using a vibrating sample magnetometer (VSM, Lake Shore VSM 7403, USA).

3 Results and Discussion

The TG curve in Fig. 1 show a minor weight loss steps from 30 °C up to about 270 °C and two major weigh loss steps from 270 °C to 450 °C. No further weigh loss was observed up to 1200 °C. The minor weight loss was related to the loss of moisture and trapped solvent in the as-spun NiFe₂O₄/PAN composite nanofibers while the major weigh loss was due to the combustion of organic PAN matrix. On the DTA curve, main exothermic peaks were

observed at ~280 °C and ~420 °C, suggesting the thermal events related to the decomposition of Ni and Fe nitrates along with the degradation of PAN by dehydration on the polymer side chain, which was confirmed by a dramatic weight loss in TG curve at the corresponding temperature range (270 - 450 °C). The plateau formed between 450 °C and 1200 °C on the TG curve indicated the formation of crystalline NiFe₂O₄ as confirmed by XRD (Fig. 2). Figs. 2 (a), (b), and (c) show the XRD patterns of the composite nanofibers after stabilization at 280 °C for 2 h in air atmosphere and carbonization at 800, 900 and 1000 °C, respectively, for 2 h in argon atmosphere. The full NiFe₂O₄ phase was formed after carbonization at 1000 °C. The main peaks with 2θ values of about 18.37°, 30.22°, 35.60°, 37.11°, 43.25°, 47.70°, 53.73°, 57.36°, 62.91° correspond to the crystal planes (111), (220), (311), (222), (400), (331), (422), (511), (440) in the standard data (JCPD 80-0072) of crystalline NiFe₂O₄, respectively. No foreign phases were detected, proving the phase purity of the samples. A broad peak appears around $2\theta = 26.0^\circ$ indicating the formation of graphite structure [7]. This broad peak can be indexed to the peak (111) Bragg reflection derived from carbon (JCPD 75-1621). In this work, since full NiFe₂O₄ phase was formed only at 1000 °C, we tried to carbonize the composite fibers at the same temperature but the stabilization time was reduced from 2 h to 0.5 h. The result indicates that the NiFe₂O₄ phase still appears as shown in Fig. 2 (d).

Fig. 1. TG-DTA curves of thermal decomposition of the as-spun NiFe₂O₄/PAN composite nanofibers in air atmosphere.

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Fig. 2. XRD patterns of 10 wt.% carbon/ NiFe_2O_4 composite nanofibers, stabilized at 280°C for 2 h in air atmosphere and carbonized at (a) 800°C (b) 900°C and (c) 1000°C for 2 h in argon atmosphere. (d) stabilized for 0.5 h and carbonized at 1000°C .

The NiFe_2O_4 peaks became sharper and narrower, suggesting that the crystallite size increases with decreasing stabilization time. The average crystallite sizes (D) of carbon/ NiFe_2O_4 composite nanofibers was calculated from X-ray line broadening of the reflection of the most intense peak (311) using Scherrer's equation ($D=0.89\lambda/(K\cos\theta)$, where λ is the wavelength of the X-ray radiation, K is the full width at half maximum (FWHM) [8] and θ is the diffraction angle), and were found to be 30.9 and 30.1 nm for the samples of carbon/ NiFe_2O_4 composite nanofibers stabilized at 280°C for 0.5 h and 2 h, respectively.

The morphologies of non-woven electrospun and carbon/ NiFe_2O_4 composite nanofibers were examined by SEM and some typical micrographs are revealed in Fig. 3. The as-spun nanofibers (Fig. 3 (a)) appear straight and have a rough surface due to the nature of $\text{NiFe}_2\text{O}_4/\text{PAN}$ composite. Each individual was quite uniform in cross section, and the average diameter of the fibers was $\sim 875\pm 86$ nm. Fig. 3 (b) shows the carbon/ NiFe_2O_4 composite nanofibers, which the morphology could be observed without coating because of the high conductivity of carbon nanofibers. After carbonization, the porous surface and a small shrinkage with average diameter $\sim 603\pm 108$ nm due to the loss of trapped solvent and the combustion of organic PAN matrix was observed. The NiFe_2O_4

nanoparticles are clearly embedded in the carbon nanofibers as further confirmed by TEM.

TEM bright field images of carbon/ NiFe_2O_4 composite nanofibers stabilized at 280°C for 0.5 h and 2 h in air atmosphere are illustrated in Figs. 4 (a) and (b), respectively. The images showed clearly the NiFe_2O_4 nanoparticles are embedded within the carbon matrix. The corresponding selected area electron diffraction patterns of the samples show spotty ring. The diffraction rings being indexed correspond to the crystal plane in the XRD patterns, showing that the products have crystalline cubic spinel structure. An increase stabilization time results in a stronger spotty pattern, indicating a highly crystalline spinel structure. Additional diffraction spots and rings of second phases have not been found, which may reveal that there is no oxide layer around the particles [9].

(a)

(b)

Fig. 3. SEM images and distribution of diameters of (a) as spun PAN/ NiFe_2O_4 (b) carbon/ NiFe_2O_4 composite nanofibers

In order to highlight the microstructure of the nanofibers, SAXS-measurements were also carried out. Fig. 5 shows the log plot of the scattered intensity (I) as a function of the scattering vector (q). The rise of the intensity in the low q can be attributed to larger structures of the fibers. The power-law slopes (d , $I \sim q^{-d}$) of each scattering regions are non-integer indicating a fractal surface roughness [10]. This parameter also relates to the dimension structure of the primary particle of the samples. Fig. 5 (a) shows the scattering intensity profile of CNFs. There are three different slopes for q between 0.2 and 2.7 nm^{-1} . The various values reveal the CNFs are built from the different structure of primary particles, such as the agglomeration of primary nanoparticles to be large sheet ($\sim q^{-1.7}$) or to be large bulk ($\sim q^{-3.5}$) with roughness surface (see inserts). We also observe another structure with roughness surface ($\sim q^{-2.2}$) but cannot define the dimension yet. The large sheet of primary nanoparticles disappears for the samples composited with the magnetic particle as seen in Figs. 5 (b) and (c). This suggests that agglomerate of the primary nanoparticles to large bulk was present.

Fig. 5. SAXS patterns of (a) CNF, (b) and (c) carbon/ NiFe_2O_4 stabilized for 0.5 h and 2 h, respectively. All of samples were carbonized at 1000°C for 2 h in argon.

Raman spectroscopy is also a powerful tool used to further investigate the carbon fiber since it provides insight into their electronic, and vibration properties [11]. Raman spectra of PAN/ NiFe_2O_4 and carbon/ NiFe_2O_4 composite nanofibers are displayed in Figs. 6 (a) and (b), respectively. The two dominant peaks around 1343 and 1568 cm^{-1} of carbon/ NiFe_2O_4 composite nanofibers correspond to D band and G band, respectively. The G-band is attributed to the “ E_{2g2} C=C stretching vibrations” in the graphite crystallites and D-band is attributed to the disordered of carbonaceous structures [12]. This indicates that the disordered PAN component is converted into more ordered graphite crystallites. Since as-spun PAN/ NiFe_2O_4 composite nanofiber is not carbon fiber, it has no characteristic peaks at 1343 and 1568 cm^{-1} as shown in Fig. 6 (b).

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4. TEM bright field images with corresponding selected area electron diffraction (SAED) patterns of carbon/ NiFe_2O_4 composite nanofibers stabilized at 280°C for (a) 0.5 h (b) 2 h. Both samples were carbonized at 1000°C for 2 h in argon.

Fig. 6. Raman spectra of (a) PAN/ NiFe_2O_4 and (b) carbon/ NiFe_2O_4 composite nanofibers.

The magnetic properties of carbon/NiFe₂O₄ composite nanofibers stabilized at 280 °C for 0.5 h and 2 h and carbonized at 1000 °C for 2 h were investigated with a VSM at 300 K with applied fields from -5000 to 5000 Oe. The curves of the magnetization (M_s) are illustrated in Fig. 7. These hysteresis curves are typical for a soft magnetic material and demonstrate the ferromagnetic behavior with specific saturation magnetization values of 0.36 and 3.40 emu/g for the samples stabilized at 0.5 and 2 h, respectively. The M_s of carbon/NiFe₂O₄ composite nanofibers is lower than those of nanocrystalline NiFe₂O₄ (42.5 emu/g) [9], the value calculated using Neel's sub lattice theory for cubic inverse spinel NiFe₂O₄ (50 emu/g) [13] and the experimentally observed for bulk NiFe₂O₄ (56 emu/g) [14]. This can be explained by the non-magnetic material covering of PAN; the defect at the surface and the nanostructure of the samples influence on the uniformity or magnitude of magnetization by extinguishing the surface magnetic moment [15]. The coercive forces (H_c) were obtained to be 98.97 and 119.34 Oe for the samples stabilized at 0.5 and 2 h, respectively. It is seen from these results that the value of coercivity increases with increasing stabilization time. The variation of H_c is possibly related to differences in defects, domain structure, shape, critical diameter and anisotropy of the crystal [16–18].

Fig. 7. Magnetization curves of carbon/NiFe₂O₄ composite nanofibers stabilized at different time of (a) 0.5 h (b) 2 h, and carbonized at 1000 °C for 2 h in argon.

4 Conclusions

Carbon/NiFe₂O₄ composite nanofibers have been successfully fabricated using electrospinning technique. The crystal structure and morphology of the nanofibers were influenced by the carbonization temperature and the stabilization time. Full phase of NiFe₂O₄ nanoparticles embedded carbon fibers as confirmed by XRD and TEM were formed after carbonization in argon atmosphere at 1000 °C for 2 h and the shrinkage of the fibers was also obtained. Both of the 1000 °C carbonized composite samples are ferromagnetic having the specific saturation magnetization (M_s) values of 0.36 and 3.40 emu/g for the samples stabilized at 0.5 and 2 h, respectively. We believe that the electrospun carbon/NiFe₂O₄ composite nanofibers would have potential in some new applications as electronic material for energy and nanodevices.

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